

Cost benefit and life cycle analysis of recycling pathways of CFRP wastes

Y. Wei and S. A. Hadigheh

School of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, The University of Sydney, NSW 2006, Australia

yaning.wei@Sydney.edu.au

ali.hadigheh@sydney.edu.au

THE UNIVERSITY OF
SYDNEY

Table of contents

1. Research background

- Why is it important to locate appropriate FRP waste treatments?

2. Technology readiness level (TRL)

3. Cost benefit analysis of different FRP waste treatments

- Capital investment analysis

- Net profit value (NPV)

- Benefit-cost ratio (BCR)

- Difference between Australian and European markets

4. Life cycle assessment of recycled composites

- Energy consumption analysis

- Global warming potentials analysis

5. Conclusions

[1] Olofin, I. and Liu, R. (2015). The Application of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) Cables in Civil Engineering Structures. SSRG International Journal of Civil Engineering (SSRG-IJCE), 2(7), 1-5.

[2] Witik, R. A., Teuscher, R., Michaud, V., Ludwig, C. and Månson, J.-A. E. (2013). Carbon fibre reinforced composite waste: An environmental assessment of recycling, energy recovery and landfilling. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 49, 89-99.

A comprehensive evaluation of ten different CFRP and GFRP waste treatment methods (i.e. landfill, incineration, mechanical recycling, catalytic pyrolysis, oxidation, pyrolysis combined with oxidation, fluidised bed, solvolysis using alkali and acid solvents, and electrochemical methods) based on a combined CBA and LCA approach for both European and Australian markets

*Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is a systematic approach to determine the possible **benefits and related costs** presented during a certain investment period.*

*Life cycle analysis(LCA) is a well-developed evaluation method that investigates **the impact on environment and society**. My project will focus on two main factors of LCA, which are **cumulative energy demand (CED) and global warming potential/CO₂ impact**.*

Mechanical: Uses shredding, crushing or milling techniques to break down the waste into powdered or fibrous form for reuse as the filler or secondary reinforcement [3]

Pyrolysis: A thermal recycling method in which the waste is decomposed in an oxygen-free environment with/without special catalysts [4]

Oxidation: Similar to pyrolysis except the reaction occurs in the presence of the air [5]

[3] Zhou, B. (2021). Experimental study on mechanical property and microstructure of cement mortar reinforced with elaborately recycled GFRP fiber. *Cement Concrete Composites*, 117, 103908

[4] Pimenta, S. and Pinho, S.T. (2011). Recycling carbon fibre reinforced polymers for structural applications: Technology review and market outlook. *Waste Management*, 31(2), 378-392

[5] Meyer, L.O. (2009). CFRP-Recycling Following a Pyrolysis Route: Process Optimization and Potentials. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 43(9), 1121-1132

Fluidised bed: A thermal recycling method, which employs flow stream to transfer the heat to the composite waste positioned on the silica sand bed [6]

Solvolysis: A chemical recycling method where solvents are used to break down the matrix bond under a specific pressure and temperature and reclaim carbon fibre [7]

Electrochemical: Resin matrix is removed from fibre surface by using electrical power [8]

[6] Pickering, S.J. (2006). Recycling technologies for thermoset composite materials—current status. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 37(8), 1206-1215

[7] La Rosa, A.D. (2016). Recycling treatment of carbon fibre/epoxy composites: Materials recovery and characterization and environmental impacts through life cycle assessment. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 104, 17-25

[8] Sun, H.(2015). Recycling of carbon fibers from carbon fiber reinforced polymer using electrochemical method. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 78, 10-17.

Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

$$C_o = C_4 + C_5 + C_6 + C_7 + C_8 + C_9$$

$$C_4 = C_{labour} + C_{non-labour} = (1 + 1.5) \times C_1$$

$$C_6 = C_{dh}(Dt)(Wd) + C_{sh}(St)(Ws)$$

$$C_7 = dc(Wdp)$$

Costs		
	Raw material cost	C1
Capital cost	Utility cost - Rental or purchase of equipment	C2
	Site preparation - Rental or purchase of industrial land for material storage and material treatment	C3
	Operating and non-operating labour cost (e.g. administration)	C4
Operational cost	Maintenance cost (i.e. $0.02 \times$ Investment on equipment)	C5
	Waste pre-processing cost (disassembly and shredding)	C6
	Waste post-processing cost (Waste final disposal cost)	C7
	Supplies (i.e. $0.3 \times$ operating labour cost)	C8
	Cost of material transportation	C9
Benefits		
Recyclable materials recovery	Economic value of recycled fibre	B1
	Economic value of secondary products	B2
Reduction of landfill cost	Reduction in expenditure of landfill site management. This value varied for different recycling methods due to their different productivity capacity	B3
Energy recovery	Production of residue derived fuels (RDFs) from waste FRP	B4

(a)

(b)

Capital investment for different (a) CFRP, and (b) GFRP waste treatments for Australian market.

(a)

(b)

Total capital investment for different (a) CFRP, and (b) GFRP waste treatments over 10 years for Australian market.

Cost analysis results for recycling of CFRP

- Solvolysis and electrochemical methods require large amount of fund to support their daily operations, with total value over AU\$ 5×10^7 for ongoing cost for solvolysis with acid solution.
- Significant cost reduction by using the alkali solution instead of acid.
- All thermal recycling methods have modest charges on both capital and operational investment
- The general trend of cost analysis is similar for CFRP and GFRP waste as the same equipment is used for both materials.

- CFRP

- Solvolysis is able to provide the highest benefit due to high tensile capacity of reclaimed fibre after recycling process
- Pyrolysis and oxidation method is also a promising method for earning high economic returns as more secondary products and energy could be recovered via thermal degradation of the matrix.

- GFRP

- More benefit could be gained by reclaiming fibres from CFRP waste than glass fibre from GFRP waste since there is a relatively lower rate of return of investment for recycling of glass fibre.

The Net Profit Value (NPV) for different CFRP and GFRP waste treatments. The NPV is total profit earned due to recycling actions can be viewed at the end of defined investment period.

The benefit-cost ratio (BCR) for different CFRP and GFRP waste treatments. The BCR is an indicator that shows the relationship between the corresponding costs and expected benefits of a certain waste path.

$$\text{BCR} = \frac{\text{net income (total benefits - corporate income tax)}}{\text{the sum of capital cost and operational cost}}$$

Difference between net profit for Australian & European markets

- ◆ Pyrolysis and solvolysis are more promising for both Australia and Europe.
- ◆ The net profit of pyrolysis and solvolysis recycling methods is higher for European market compared with the Australian one.
- ◆ These variations in benefit are due to technological advancement and availability of renewable energy infrastructures during recycling process in each region, and government supports.

- ◆ Cumulative energy demand (CED)
- ◆ It also could be used as a framework by industry for decision making on selecting recycling technique by considering energy consumption intensity, especially in relation to non-renewable energy use for each treatment method
- ◆ Sensitivity analysis based on waste capacity for CED: four levels of processing capacity were tested for investigating the impact of input quantity on CED, which are 1,000, 2,000, 3,000 and 6,000 tonnes

- ◆ Global warming potentials (GWPs) --- the impact of different greenhouse gases in the atmosphere
- ◆ Lower value indicates lower negative impact on the environment and the negative value means the reduction of greenhouse gas.

Cost-benefit analysis:

- ◆ Solvolysis could provide highest profit due to its high value of net profit.
- ◆ The performance of solvolysis could vary by using different chemical solutions. Solvolysis with acid solution requires higher capital investment and produces less value of recycled fibre after acidification.
- ◆ Thermal recycling methods such as catalytic pyrolysis and pyrolysis plus oxidation also provide high economic return.
- ◆ Electrochemical method requires large operational cost.
- ◆ The economic returns of different recycling techniques performed slightly different for Australian and European markets.

Life cycle analysis:

- ◆ Thermal recycling methods require low energy input with reasonable expected economic profit. Compared with pyrolysis combined with oxidation, electrochemical method requires large amount of electricity to obtain similar profit.
- ◆ GWP impact analysis showed that solvolysis and electrochemical methods have lowest CO₂ emission during recycling while landfill, incineration and fluidised bed treatments cannot satisfy the expectations of CO₂ emission reduction and may contribute to global warming.

Acknowledgement

Contact us:

Yaning Wei (yaning.wei@sydney.edu.au)

Ali Hadigheh (ali.hadigheh@sydney.edu.au)